

INTERFACES FOR IMPROVED SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PHENOLIC COMPOSITES

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SYNOPSIS

The bimatrix fragmentation test, in which the failure strain of the matrix is less than that of the fibre, has been used to determine the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface. This test is based on the well established single filament fragmentation test. The finite element method has been used to analyse the stress profile in the specimen, which demonstrated that the bimatrix fragmentation test is a viable method for the determination of the interfacial shear strength of the phenolic composites.

The interfacial shear strength of an as-received unsized uncoupled glass fibre in the bimatrix fragmentation test specimen was used as the reference. The as-received unsized uncoupled fibre was subjected to a number of surface treatments, including silane coupling agents and epoxy resin solution. It was found that several fibre surface treatments yielded higher interfacial shear strength than the untreated glass fibre.

INTRODUCTION

The excellent fire resistance of the thermosetting phenolic resin, combined with its low smoke and toxic fume emission [1] have prompted greater interest in the development of high-performance phenolic resin based fibre composites for engineering applications in recent years. This development requires a detailed study of the variables that uniquely correlate the micromechanics to the mechanical performance of the composites. Through our research [2,3], it was concluded that the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin matrix interface is very low, and the bonding between the two constituents is dominated by friction. In order to improve the mechanical properties of the composites, a stronger interface is required.

The most commonly used method for the determination of the interfacial shear strength is the single filament fragmentation test [4-12]. In this test a single fibre is embedded in a flexible matrix, and a tensile test is carried out. As the applied strain increases, the tensile stress in the fibre will increase until it exceeds the failure strength of the fibre. The fibre will fracture. This process continues until the fibre fragments are too small to be stressed to fracture, and the

saturation in fragment length has occurred. According to Ohsawa et al [6], the critical fibre length l_c can be calculated by

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3} \bar{l} \quad (1)$$

and the interfacial shear strength τ by [13]

$$\tau = \frac{r_f \sigma_c}{l_c} \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{l} is the average fragment length, r_f the fibre radius and σ_c the ultimate tensile strength of the fibre at critical fibre length.

In order to reach the saturation fragment length, the failure strain of the matrix is required to be three times of that of the fibre, so the fragmentation test cannot be used for brittle matrix composites.

Favre et al [12,14] introduced the bimatrix fragmentation test: the single glass fibre is coated with a thin sheath of the relevant matrix, and embedded in a more ductile support matrix. It was speculated that when this specimen is loaded in tension, the fibre will fracture and cause a transverse fracture of the brittle sheath which will be prevented from growing by the ductile support matrix. As the applied tensile strain increases, the glass fibre will fracture continuously until saturation. The critical fibre length and the interfacial shear strength can still be calculated by Eqns (1) and (2).

The conventional bimatrix fragmentation test proposed by Favre et al [12,14] still requires that the failure strain of the brittle matrix is greater than that of the glass fibre, so that the fibre fractures first. But the failure strain of the phenolic resin is less than 1% [15], much less than that of the glass fibre, being 2.5 - 4.0% [16]. The finite element method has been used to study the suitability of the bimatrix fragmentation test technique for phenolic composites. The effect of fibre treatments on the interfacial shear strength of glass fibre - phenolic matrix interface was also investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two as-received unsized uncoupled glass fibres were used, PPG glass fibre (PPG Glassfibers Ltd) and OCF glass fibre (Owens-Corning Fiberglas). Analysis of the fibres by X-photoelectron spectroscopy and time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry has shown that there is no silane coupling agents present on the fibre surface. The glass fibres were treated in the laboratory with the following fibre treatments: (a) epoxysilane coupling agent A187 (Union Carbide), (b) aminosilane coupling agent A1100 (Union Carbide) followed by epoxy resin Epikote 828 (Shell Chemicals), and (c) epoxy resin Epikote 828.

Two novolac phenolic resins were used, CS366 (TBA Composites) and IR2245 (Hepworth Minerals and Chemicals). It was observed that the failure strain of the IR2245 phenolic resin is 0.6% [15].

Two support resins were used; A vinyl ester resin Derakane 411-45 (Dow Chemicals), was cured with 1.0% v/w of cobalt soap Accelerator E, 0.5% v/w of DMA Accelerator D and 2.0% v/w of MEKP Catalyst M (Scott Bader) at room temperature for 24 hours before testing; An epoxy resin, 52 phr Epikote 828 resin (Shell Chemicals) with 48 phr Araldite GY298 (Ciba-Geigy), was cured with 80 phr nadic methylene anhydride (NMA) (Astor-Stag Ltd) and 40 phr Capcure 3-800 (Henkel Corporation) at 55°C for 18 hours and 130°C for 3 hours before cooling naturally in the oven to room temperature.

A single fibre separated from the as-received or treated fibre bundles, was coated with a thin layer of phenolic resin by pulling it through a small orifice covered with a 50% w/w solution in industrial methylated spirit (IMS). The phenolic resin in the coating was then cured at 165°C for 5 minutes. The preparation of the fragmentation test specimens and the test procedures are given elsewhere [15,17].

The fibre diameter was measured with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The tensile strengths of single glass filaments at a gauge length of 6.35 mm were determined, as described elsewhere [7]. Fibre strength σ_c at the critical fibre length can be calculated from the Weibull distribution as follows [18]:

$$\sigma_l / \sigma_c = (l_c / l_l)^{1/m} \quad (3)$$

Where σ_l is the fibre strength at fibre length l_l of 6.35 mm, and m the Weibull modulus.

The critical fibre length and interfacial shear strength of the single glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites were determined by the bimatix fragmentation technique. The individual fragment lengths in the specimen after tensile testing were accurately measured using an image analyser. The critical fibre length required for the calculation of the interfacial shear strength was obtained from the average fragment length according to Eqn (1), and the interfacial shear strength calculated from Eqn (2). The fibre strength at the critical length was obtained by Eqn (3). The standard deviation of the interfacial shear strength was calculated with a computer programme developed at the University of Sheffield [10].

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS MODEL

A single glass fibre, with a diameter of 15.2 μm and a length of 1.3 mm, was enclosed in a concentric cylinder of phenolic resin of thickness 1.5 μm , embedded in a block of epoxy resin 0.55 mm in diameter and 1.8 mm in length, as shown in Fig. 1(a). Because of the axial symmetry, only one quarter of the 2D axisymmetric model was used for the finite element analysis, as shown in Fig. 1(b). Another model with a transverse fracture in the phenolic coating at the mid-length was also built [15]. The load was gradually applied on surface CD in the Y direction. Surfaces AD and AB were constrained in X and Y directions respectively.

The nominal stress - strain curve of the epoxy support resin was experimentally obtained from a tensile test. The epoxy resin yielded at about 3% of applied strain, followed by necking at higher applied strain. The tensile yield strength of the epoxy resin was 40.8 MPa and necking strength 31.7 MPa. Both the glass fibre and the phenolic resin are elastic, isotropic materials.

The finite element solver used was ABAQUS version 5.3 (Hibbitt, Karlsson and Sorenson Inc. USA), a powerful general purpose finite element solver. The results were analysed with ABAQUS Post. The details of the mesh and the analysis procedure are given elsewhere [15,17].

Figure 1. (a). The geometry and (b) the model used for the finite element analysis of bimatix fragmentation test (not drawn to scale).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The tensile strain at the centre of the phenolic resin coating along the length direction at different applied strains is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. The tensile strain at the centre of the coating along the length direction at different applied strains (Applied strains: \diamond , 0.75%; \triangle , 1.50%; \square , 2.50%).

(a). no transverse fracture of the coating, and (b). with one transverse fracture of the coating.

It can be seen from Fig. 2(a) that when the applied strain is 0.75%, the strain at the mid-length of the coating has exceeded the failure strain of the phenolic resin, being 0.6%, consequently the

coating at the mid-length will fracture transversely. Based on this result, a second model was built, as described earlier, with a transverse fracture in the coating at the mid-length. The profile of the tensile strain in the coating for the second model is shown in Fig. 2(b). It can be seen that when the applied strain is about 0.75%, the strain in the coating near the mid-length position has once again exceeded the failure strain of the phenolic resin, consequently another transverse fracture will occur in the coating near the mid-length. Further application of tensile strain on the model will result in more transverse fractures of the coating near the mid-length.

The shear stress at the fibre - phenolic resin interface in the two above mentioned models at different applied strains is shown in Fig. 3. Comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) it can be seen that the transverse fracture of the phenolic resin coating does not affect the shear stress development at the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface. The only difference between the two figures is the singularity at the mid-length where the transverse fracture of the coating exists. It can also be seen that shear stress is zero at the mid fibre length, rises to a peak value before decreasing near the fibre ends. At higher applied strains, a plateau value of the shear stress appears. There are two distinctive values of the shear stress, peak and plateau values. The peak value of the shear stress is 24 - 27 MPa depending on the applied strain, and the plateau value 22 - 23 MPa. The shear stress at the phenolic resin - epoxy support resin interface was also calculated. It was found that both of the peak and plateau values of the shear stress were lower than those at the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface respectively, and were 20 - 23 MPa and 18 MPa respectively. The peak and plateau values of shear stress at both interfaces are a result of yielding and necking of the epoxy resin, and are approximately $1/\sqrt{3}$ times of the tensile yield and necking strengths of the epoxy resin respectively [15,17].

Figure 3. The shear stress at the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface at different applied strains (Applied strains: \circ - 0.50%; \triangle - 1.50%; \square - 2.50%).
 (a). no transverse fracture of the coating, and (b). with one transverse fracture of the coating.

The tensile stress at the centre of the fibre along the fibre length direction was also calculated. It was found that the tensile stress development in the two models was identical, irrespective of the existence of the transverse fracture of the coating. This implies that the transverse fracture, and hence the failure strain of the phenolic resin coating, do not affect the stress transfer from the phenolic resin coating to the fibre.

Hence chronologically when the bimatrix fragmentation test specimen is loaded in tension, the phenolic resin coating will first fracture transversely, and as the applied strain increases the phenolic resin coating will further fracture into several segments. The applied load is transferred

to the fibre through the fibre - phenolic interface, and when the applied strain is high enough the fibre will fracture. As the applied strain increases the fibre will continue to fracture until saturation. The interfacial shear strength of the fibre - phenolic interface will determine the final fragment length, so bimatrix fragmentation technique can be used to measure the interfacial shear strength of phenolic composites.

INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH DETERMINATION

The tensile strength of the two as-received glass fibres was measured at a gauge length of 6.35 mm, and the results are presented in Table 1. The Weibull modulus m of the fibres was calculated with the maximum likelihood method [10,18]. The average fibre diameters are also presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The properties of the two as-received glass fibres (standard deviation in brackets).

Glass fibres	PPG fibre	OCF fibre
Tensile strength at length = 6.35 mm (GPa)	2.375 (0.480)	2.077 (0.473)
Weibull modulus m	5.342	5.000
Average fibre diameter (μm)	15.2	14.52

The critical fibre length and interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites were determined by the bimatrix fragmentation technique. The critical fibre length and the interfacial shear strength of PPG glass fibre in CS366 phenolic resin with vinyl ester support resin and in Hepworth IR2245 phenolic resin with epoxy support resin are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The critical fibre length and the interfacial shear strength for PPG glass fibre with different fibre treatments (standard deviation in brackets).

Fibre treatments	Phenolic resin	Support resin	l_c (mm)	τ (MPa)
As-received	CS366	Vinyl ester	2.02 (0.73)	11.05 (2.31)
A1100 + Epikote 828	CS366	Vinyl ester	1.26 (0.35)	19.48 (4.07)
As-received	IR2245	Epoxy resin	0.63 (0.15)	43.91 (9.34)
Epoxy 828	IR2245	Epoxy resin	0.53 (0.12)	54.38 (11.56)

It can be seen from Table 2 that the fibres treated with Epikote 828 with or without pre-treatment of A1100 aminosilane coupling agent have much higher interfacial shear strength in glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites than the as-received fibres. It is well known that epoxy resins react with phenolic resins through phenolic hydroxyl and epoxide groups:

Further reaction of the hydroxyl and epoxide groups can occur. The epoxy treatment acts as an interlayer, linking the glass fibre and the phenolic resin together, and hence improves the interfacial shear strength.

The interfacial shear strengths τ for the as-received fibre are very different with the two different support resins, as shown in Table 2. This is because of the difference in the yield strengths of the support resins. The tensile yield strength of the vinyl ester support resin is 18.5 MPa and the epoxy support resin 40.8 MPa. As demonstrated by the finite element analysis [15,17], the shear stress at the fibre - matrix interface is strongly influenced by the yield strength of the support matrix, and a higher yield strength of the support matrix will result in a higher value of τ .

A SEM has been used to examine the tensile fracture surface of bimatrix fragmentation test specimens. The fracture surface of two bimatrix specimens, one with the as-received fibre, and another with A1100 + Epikote 828 treated fibre, with CS366 phenolic resin coating in vinyl ester support resin was examined. Multiple transverse fractures of the phenolic resin coating were observed in both specimens. It was also found that with the as-received unsized uncoupled glass fibre, the failure occurred at the glass fibre - phenolic resin coating interface, while with the A1100 + Epikote 828 treated glass fibre, the failure occurred at the phenolic resin coating - vinyl ester support resin interface. This indicates that in the case of the as-received glass fibre the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface is less than that of the phenolic resin - vinyl ester resin interface, while with the A1100 + Epikote 828 treated glass fibre the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface is greater than that at the phenolic resin - vinyl ester resin interface. Therefore it can be concluded that the interfacial shear strength with A1100 + Epikote 828 fibre treatment is greater than that with as-received unsized uncoupled glass fibre, this is in good agreement with the bimatrix fragmentation test results (Table 2), indicating that the bimatrix fragmentation test is a suitable technique to determine the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites.

The critical fibre length and the interfacial shear strength of the OCF glass fibre in the phenolic resin IR2245 were also determined. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The critical fibre length and the interfacial shear strength for OCF glass fibre in IR2245 phenolic resin with epoxy support resin with different fibre treatments (standard deviation in brackets).

Fibre treatments	l_c (mm)	τ (MPa)
As-received	0.63 (0.15)	37.78 (9.98)
A187 (45°C dried)	0.61 (0.13)	39.71 (10.49)
A187 (130°C dried)	0.56 (0.12)	44.24 (11.70)

It can be seen from Table 3 that with A187 silane coupling agent treatment, the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface is also improved. A187 is an epoxysilane coupling agent, and it will probably react with phenolic resin similarly to the epoxy resin.

CONCLUSIONS

The stress transfer in the bimatrix fragmentation specimen has been successfully predicted with finite element analysis. It was found that the phenolic coating will fracture transversely during bimatrix fragmentation test, and as the applied strain increases, the coating will fracture repeatedly. The fibre fragment length is related to the interfacial shear strength of the fibre - phenolic resin interface, hence bimatrix fragmentation test can be used to examine adhesion.

The interfacial shear strength obtained from the bimatrix fragmentation test is influenced by the yield strength of the support matrix.

Using bimatrix fragmentation tests, it was found that glass fibre treatments with Epikote 828 epoxy resin and A187 epoxysilane coupling agent have significantly improved the interfacial shear strength of the glass fibre - phenolic resin interface.

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REFERENCES

1. K. L. Forsdyke, *The 16th Reinforced Plastics Congress*, British Plastics Federation, Reinforced Plastics Group (1988) pp 9-13.
2. F. Chen and F. R. Jones, *Thermoset'91, Physical Performance and High Volume Manufacture*, The Reinforced Plastics and Composites Group, The Plastics and Rubber Institute, London, (23 - 24 April 1991), pp10/1-10/11.
3. F. Chen and F. R. Jones, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites Processing and Applications*, In press.
4. W. A. Fraser, F. H. Ancker and A. T. DiBenedetto, *Proceedings of 30th Anniversary Technical Conference, 1975, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, Society of Plastics Industry, Inc*, Section 22-A.
5. J.-P. Favre, P. Sigety and D. Jacques, *Journal of Materials Science*, **26** (1991) 189-195.
6. T. Ohsawa, A. Nakayama, M. Miwa and A. Hasegawa, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **22** (1978) 3203-3212.
7. T.H. Cheng, F.R. Jones and D. Wang, *Composite Science and Technology*, **48** (1993) 89-96.
8. E. M. Asloun, M. Nardin and J. Schultz, *Journal of Material Science*, **24** (1989) 1835-1844.
9. A. N. Netravali, R. B. Henstenburg, et al, *Polymer Composite*, **10** (1989) 226-241.
10. T. H. Cheng, J. Zhang, S. Yumitori, F. R. Jones, et al, *Composites*, **25** (1994) 661 - 670.
11. J.-P. Favre, *Proceedings of International Conference on Interfacial Phenomena in Composite Materials '89*, Sheffield (9/1989). Ed: F. R. Jones (Butterworths, London), 7-12.
12. J.-P. Favre and D. Jacques, *Journal of Material Science*, **25** (1990) 1373-1380.
13. A. Kelly and W. R. Tyson, *Journal of Mechanics of Physical Solids*, **13** (1965) 329-350.
14. D. Jacques and J.-P. Favre, *Proceedings of the sixth International Conference on Composite Materials and second European Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM VI & ECCM 2)*, London, July 1987, Volume 5, Edited by F.L. Matthews, N.C.R. Buskell, J.M. Hodgkinson and J. Morton. (Elsevier Applied Science, London), p471.
15. F. Chen, D. Tripathi and F. R. Jones, *Progress Reports No 4-9, Department of Engineering Materials, The University of Sheffield* (1994-5), Unpublished results.
16. J. Klunder, *Silenka Service Manual on Glass Fibres*, N V Silenka, the Netherlands (1970) 17.
17. D. Tripathi, F. Chen and F. R. Jones, *The Royal Society Proceedings: Mathematical and Physical Sciences*. Submitted.
18. A. Khalili and K. Kromp, *Journal of Material Science*, **26** (1991) 6741-6752.